

Detecting Strategic Neologisms in Ideological Online Discourses: A System for Topic and Query Extraction

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1. Introduction

This study develops a system for the automated extraction and analysis of keywords and keyphrases from online texts. The goal is to identify new terms that are not yet included in established dictionaries in order to examine linguistic developments in various digital discourses. The starting point is the observation that alternative online platforms, particularly in the left-wing and right-wing spectrum, are increasingly acting as catalysts for ideological narratives. These platforms frequently contribute to the creation and spread of strategic neologisms that fill so-called *data voids* (Golebiewski & Boyd, 2019), i.e., thematic areas with little to no reliable information online (Haider u. Sundin 2019, pp. 41–42). These voids are filled with placed content aimed at advancing a specific agenda and users are directed toward it through recommended search terms on social media (Haider & Sundin 2019, pp. 41–42). As a result, these manipulated contents appear prominently in search results and are perceived as trustworthy (Golebiewski & Boyd 2019; Haider & Sundin 2019).

Through web crawling and scraping, content from such websites is collected and analyzed using modern natural language processing (NLP) methods, as well as rule- and statistic-based techniques to identify potentially new or ideologically charged terms. The textual data undergoes preprocessing steps including sentence segmentation and noise filtering to remove generic and irrelevant content. Language detection is performed through both stopword-based heuristics and probabilistic classifiers to ensure proper handling of multilingual data. For linguistic annotation, state-of-the-art NLP models such as spaCy are employed to carry out tokenization (Altinok, 2021), part-of-speech tagging (Altinok, 2021), and syntactic parsing, enabling the extraction of linguistically meaningful units. Keyphrase extraction is based on a combination of frequency analysis, *n*-grams, and a sliding-window technique to capture relevant multi-word expressions, particularly adjective-noun and verb-noun constructions (Jurafsky & Martin, 2013; Steur & Schwenker, 2021; Ganardi et al., 2018). To validate potential neologisms, the system cross-references with established linguistic resources such as WordNet, GermaNet and the Leipzig Corpora Collection. In doing so, it analyzes the temporal spread of new terms, identifies linguistic shifts and uncovers thematic trends in articles and user comments. Particular attention is given to the second form of *data voids* in this study described by Norocel and Lewandowski (2023): strategic new terms created within extremist networks to introduce problematic interpretations and gradually shift discourse boundaries. Since such terms are often not included in established dictionaries, their identification and analysis are essential.

This study complements recent research such as the work by Das and Senapati (2024), who investigated the automatic detection of hate-related neologisms in the Bengali election context. Their approach utilizes Twitter data combined with rule-based filters to identify new terms associated with hate speech and sarcasm. While both studies share the goal of detecting socially

relevant neologisms through automated means, they differ significantly in methodology, data sources, and filtering strategies. Das and Senapati (2024) manually annotate whether a neologism contains hate or sarcasm. Their results show that rule-based filters combined with manual classification can be effective methods for identifying hate-related neologisms. Whereas Das and Senapati (2024) explicitly categorize individual terms as hate or sarcasm, this study follows an exploratory approach. Instead of labeling words individually, it analyzes how neologisms spread over time, which ideological patterns can be identified, and which terms gain traction within online communities.

A similar long-term analysis of neologisms is conducted by Kerremans and Prokić (2018) using a semi-automatic system called NeoCrawler. Their method relies on dictionary-based string matching against a Wikipedia dump to propose potential neologisms, which must then be manually validated before being monitored long-term. In contrast, the present study does not explicitly classify extracted terms as neologisms or non-neologisms. Instead, all candidates serve as a basis for further analysis. Given the large number of potential neologisms (approx. 580,000), full manual classification is impractical and limited to sampling for evaluation purposes only. Moreover, while the NeoCrawler module tracks only confirmed neologisms over time, this study monitors all identified candidates regardless of manual validation. Another key difference is the ability to detect multi-word expressions (e.g., adjective-noun and verb-noun phrases), which Kerremans and Prokić note as a limitation of their unigram-based approach. Nevertheless, they emphasize that their system enables effective automatic identification of potential neologisms and achieves high accuracy in detecting new words.

This study examines seven ideologically distinct online platforms associated with either the far-left or far-right spectrum: *sezession.de*, *blauenarzisse.de*, *schweizerzeit.ch*, *de.indymedia.org*, *antifainfoblatt.de*, *antifa-info.net*, and *der-rechte-rand.de*. The selection was theory-driven, based on their documented relevance in political science research and constitutional protection reports, as well as their discursive influence within respective political milieus. The subsequent automated analysis demonstrates that the developed methodology is capable of reliably identifying the central thematic priorities of the platforms under investigation. The extracted keywords and keyphrases reflect each platform's ideological orientation and offer insight into typical semantic patterns and recurring narratives within their discursive environments.

The analysis reveals that right-wing discourses are often shaped by ethnonationalist concepts, migration-critical language, media hostility and metapolitical strategies, while left-wing discourses focus on antifascism, social justice, criticism of capitalism and state repression.

On the examined websites, the focus was more on the creation of new terms, while the reuse of previously identified potential neologisms was comparatively rarer. This indicates that the platforms under study continuously generate new linguistic concepts. Such strategic neologisms created by extremist groups aim to fill semantic gaps intentionally in order to gain interpretive power in the digital space. The developed system enables the early identification of such terms and their analysis in the process of normalizing extremist narratives.

The study discusses methodological challenges such as language confusion, generic terms and the potential for enhancing the semantic analysis of longer or more complex phrases. Finally, it explores perspectives for further integrating the system into areas like semantic media analysis, SEO research or digital radicalization prevention. The extracted keywords and phrases could also be used in future studies to query search engines and assess how a website ranks in comparison to competing platforms. This approach may be particularly relevant for analyzing the visibility and spread of ideological narratives in search results. Through its multilingual architecture and adaptability to various types of websites, the system offers an innovative contribution to the linguistic, media and social science analysis of ideological online communication. It is not limited to right-wing and left-wing platforms but can be applied to a wide range of online communities and discourses.

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3. References

Altinok, Duygu: Mastering spaCy. Packt Publishing, 2021 <https://learning.oreilly.com/library/view/mastering-spacy/9781800563353/>

Das, Sujit & Senapati, Apurbalal. (2024). Hate Neologism in Election Context in India. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/9781394248438.ch31>

Ganardi, Moses ; Hucke, Danny ; Lohrey, Markus: Randomized sliding window algorithms for regular languages. (2018), 02. – <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1802.07600>

Golebiewski, Michael & boyd, danah. (2019). Data Voids: Where Missing Data Can Easily Be Exploited. *Data & Society* (2019), October. <https://www.microsoft.com/en-us/research/publication/data-voids-where-missing-data-can-easily-be-exploited/>

Haider, J., & Sundin, O. (2019). *Invisible Search and Online Search Engines: The Ubiquity of Search in Everyday Life* (1st ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429448546>

Jurafsky, Daniel ; Martin, James: *Speech and Language Processing* Pearson New International Edition. Pearson Deutschland, 2013. – <https://elibrary.pearson.de/book/99.150005/9781292037936>

Kerremans, Daphné ; Prokić, Jelena: Mining the Web for New Words: Semi-Automatic Neologism Identification with the NeoCrawler. In: *Anglia* 136 (2018), Nr. 2, S. 239–268. – <https://doi.org/10.1515/ang-2018-0032>

Norocel, O. C., & Lewandowski, D. (2023). Google, data voids, and the dynamics of the politics of exclusion. *Big Data & Society*, 10(1), <https://doi.org/10.1177/20539517221149099> (Original work published 2023)

Steur, Nikolai A. K. ; Schwenker, Friedhelm: Next-Generation Neural Networks: Capsule Networks With Routing-by-Agreement for Text Classification. In: *IEEE Access* 9 (2021), S. 125269–125299. – <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2021.3110911>